

CPMAS ^{13}C NMR SPECTROSCOPY AS A TOOL TO STUDY THE IMPACT OF BIOSTIMULANT AND SUBSTRATE COMPOSITION ON LETTUCE GROWTH

Álvaro F. García-Rodríguez^a, Francisco J. Moreno-Racero^a, Miguel A. Rosales^b,
Heike Knicker^a

^aGroup of Interactions Between Soils, Plants and Microorganisms,
Instituto de la Grasa, (IG-CSIC), 41013 Sevilla, Spain.

^bDepartment of Stress, Development and Signaling in Plants,
Estación Experimental del Zaidín (EEZ-CSIC), 18008 Granada, Spain

*email: alvaro.garcia@csic.es

Keywords: Flavonoid, peat substrate, compost-biochar mixture, plant health

During the last years, the use of biochar or compost as substitutes for peat in horticulture has gained interest [1]. However, there are still knowledge gaps on the effect of these substitutes on plant and soil growing parameters. Bearing in mind the increasing costs of fertilizers, especially for N and P and the need of reducing the use of pesticides, have encouraged the application of bio-stimulant products, among others, for sustainable agriculture. In this work, we studied the suitability of organic horticulture substrates as biochar, peat and compost mixtures for lettuce growth (*Lactuca sativa* L. var) by analyzing the ^{13}C CPMAS NMR spectra and the relative abundance of C functional groups to identify the chemical features of organic matter.

The substrate mixtures used (peat:biochar:compost:vermiculite) were as follows: 70:0:0:30 (PB0), 40:5:25:30 (PB5), 0:0:70:30 (CB0); 0:15:55:30 (CB15), 0:30:40:30 (CB30) and 0:50:20:30 (CB50). In addition, plants were treated with flavonoid-based biostimulant. Organic substrate mixtures were characterized by elemental and chemical parameters and CPMAS ^{13}C NMR spectroscopy at the beginning and end of plant bioassay during 40 days after plant sowing.

The NMR spectra revealed that C distribution in the substrate mixtures with and without bio stimulant treatment correlated differently with shoot and root growth. PCA provided a satisfactory ordination of the chemical parameters in relation to the sensitivity of the tested plants, with eigenvalues of the first two components accounting for 83.32% (51.22 and 32.1%) and 86.41% (61.81 and 24.60%) of the total variance for substrates of control and biostimulated plants, respectively. For 40-DAS-substrates in the control experiments, the first and second PCA components highlight the link of phenol C and aryl C with shoot growth whereas O-alkyl C being more associated with root development. In contrast, PCA for 40 DAS substrates for the experiments with bio stimulant showed a relation of carboxyl C or N/methoxyl C contents with root dry biomass and the proportion of O-alkyl C with shoot growth. Lettuce growth can also be explained by the negative correlations with carbonyl C, alkyl C and N/methoxyl C contents in substrates in the control experiments.

References:

[1] García-Rodríguez, Á. F., Moreno-Racero, F. J., García de Castro Barragán, J. M., Colmenero-Flores, J. M., Greggio, N., Knicker, H., & Rosales, M. A. (2022). Influence of Biochar Mixed into Peat Substrate on Lettuce Growth and Nutrient Supply. *Horticulturae*, 8(12), 1214.

Acknowledgments and Funding:

The “Gruppo Caviro” and “Green Valley Solutions” are thanked for providing the biochar and the bio-stimulant, respectively. Laura Gismero and Rocio Reinoso are gratefully acknowledged for their technical assistance. The work was funded by TwinSubDyn project (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-01).